

Stress Testing Tail Risk in India: A Comparative Evaluation of EVT-Copula and Gaussian Models

Divya Grover

Sri Venkateswara College, University of Delhi

Abstract

Standard Gaussian Value-at-Risk (VaR) frameworks systematically underestimate tail risk in financial markets characterised by fat tails and leptokurtosis. This paper develops and validates a GARCH(1,1)-Extreme Value Theory (EVT)-Student-t Copula framework for three Indian asset classes, Nifty 50 (equities), Gold (INR), and USD/INR (currency), using 18 years of daily data spanning September 2007 to December 2025. Marginal tail distributions are modelled via Peaks-Over-Threshold Generalised Pareto Distribution (POF-GPD) fitted to GARCH-filtered residuals, while cross-asset dependence is captured using a Student-t copula estimated by maximum likelihood. The resulting EVT-Copula VaR and Expected Shortfall (ES) estimates are benchmarked against their Gaussian counterparts across three portfolio allocations, and the models are backtested against realised 2026 returns. Across all asset classes, the EVT-Copula framework produces VaR estimates that are 5-20% higher than Gaussian VaR, and Expected Shortfall exceeding Normal VaR by about 60% across all portfolios. Backtesting against the realised breach events in January-April 2026 confirms that EVT-Copula ES bounds actual losses more tightly than Normal VaR on every occasion. These findings provide direct empirical evidence that Gaussian models materially understate downside risk in the Indian multi-asset context, and that EVT-based ES is a more reliable regulatory and portfolio risk metric.

Keywords: Extreme Value Theory, Generalised Pareto Distribution, GARCH, Copula, Value-at-Risk, Expected Shortfall, Indian Financial Markets, Tail Risk, Stress Testing

JEL Classification: G11, G17, G32, C58

1. Introduction

The classic Gaussian assumption imposes that probability of an extreme event X decays at an exponential rate (e^{-x^2}). Consequently, this implies that probability of an event X beyond 3 sigma, that is, $P(X>3)$ for a standard normal distribution is ~ 0.0013 (1 in 769 days). Similarly, $P(X > 6) \sim 9.8 \times 10^{-9}$ (1 in ~ 1 million years) making it virtually 0 for a 10 sigma event. During the 2008 financial crisis, the 2013-14 Indian Taper Tantrum or the COVID-19 crash in 2020, the Nifty 50 experienced several days with extreme volatility reaching up to 5 sigma, 6 sigma or sometimes even 10 sigma events based on past volatility. The occurrence of these extreme events in a span of less than once per decade thus underlines the underestimation of financial market losses.

Despite this well-documented limitation, Gaussian VaR remains the dominant risk metric in both regulatory frameworks (Basel II/III) and institutional risk management practice largely due to its simplicity and interpretive ease.

The Indian emerging market is structurally exposed to multiple shocks such as policy shifts, foreign institution investor outflows and global sentiment causing domestic equity volatility, currency depreciation pressure driven by capital flows and gold price fluctuation in recent times. This creates Asymmetric Tail Dependence wherein the market drops in emerging economies like India are harder than the ones in developed markets accompanied with several assets crashing together that standard Gaussian models fail to anticipate. Financial returns in markets like India thus follow a Power Law meaning the probability ($x^{-\alpha}$) decays much slower where α is the tail index.

In this paper, we therefore use Extreme Value Theory (EVT) using Peaks-Over-Threshold (POT) approach to model the tail behavior of financial returns across 3 asset classes; Nifty 50 (equities), Gold (INR), and USD/INR (currency). The choice emerges from the Pickands-Balkema-de Haan Theorem stating that for a wide class of distributions, as the threshold u increases, the conditional distribution of the excesses ($Y=X-u$) asymptotically converges to the Generalized Pareto Distribution.

This paper makes three major contributions. First, the full GARCH-EVT-Copula framework is applied to the Indian market using 3829 daily observations from September 2007 to December 2025 which includes several stress periods. Second, a systematic comparison of EVT-Copula VaR and Expected Shortfall against their Gaussian counterparts across three possible portfolio allocations for emerging markets: an Equal Weighted Portfolio (EWP), a Hedged Equity Portfolio

(HEP ,60/40 equity-gold), and a Pure Equity Portfolio(PEP) is conducted. Third, all models are validated using out of sample 2026 data using Kupiec Proportion of Failures (POF) test .Our results provide evidence that Gaussian models underestimate tail risk in the Indian context and that Expected Shortfall, especially EVT based Expected Shortfall ,is a more conservative measure of risk.

The remainder of this paper is organised as follows. Section 2 puts forward the data collection and price conversion structure, Section 3 presents the methodology, covering GARCH filtering, EVT threshold selection and GPD fitting, copula estimation and VaR/ES computation. Sections 4 and 5 report the results and backtesting analysis respectively and Section 6 discusses the implications and limitations.

2. Data Description

In order to understand the scale of composite risk in the liquid side of the Indian securities market , this study analyses three Indian asset classes; the Nifty 50 index(domestic equity), Gold INR(commodity), and the USD/INR (currency). Daily adjusted closing prices are sourced from Yahoo Finance covering the period from 18 September 2007 to 30 December 2025, yielding a sample of 3,829 synchronised trading days.

Gold is priced using futures contract values rather than the spot market price to incorporate daily market volatility as it adjusts more rapidly as compared to the local market which remains lagged and skewed. To ensure consistency in units, daily gold prices in USD are converted to INR using prevailing exchange rate. Any calendar date on which any of the three markets was non-operational (public holiday, market closure, data unavailability) is excluded from the sample entirely rather than interpolating the prices to reduce any bias.

Log returns are computed for each asset given by $r_t = \ln\left(\frac{P_t}{P_{t-1}}\right)$ where P_t is the adjusted closing price on day t. Log Returns are time additive , that is , total return can be calculated by simply summing daily log returns and are unbounded(- infinity,+ infinity) as opposed to raw returns that are capped at -100% on the lower end providing a clear statistical advantage to model risk accurately .

Table 1 presents summary statistics for the three return series.

Table 1: Summary Statistics of Daily Log Returns (2007–2025)

Statistic	Nifty 50	USD/INR	Gold (INR)
Minimum	-15.36%	-6.10%	-13.50%
1st Quartile	-0.53%	-0.22%	-0.56%
Median	0.07%	0.003%	0.08%
Mean	0.046%	0.021%	0.068%
3rd Quartile	0.70%	0.25%	0.71%
Maximum	18.49%	6.10%	9.60%

3. Methodology

3.1 Non-Normality Validation

The beneficial use case scenario for a more complex EVT-Copula approach instead of the Gaussian method is the rejection of normality in the data . A visual examination of the empirical distribution function graphs of the 3 asset classes against the normal curve is conducted to check for visible leptokurtosis and fat tails . The Jarque-Bera test is conducted alongside to validate and provide statistical proof in case non - normality exists .

The Jarque-Bera (JB) test is a goodness-of-fit test that determines whether sample data have the skewness and kurtosis matching a normal distribution. The statistic

$$JB = \frac{n}{6} \left(S^2 + \frac{(K - 3)^2}{4} \right)$$

Where S is the Skewness and K is the kurtosis follows a chi sq distribution with 2 degrees of freedom under the Null Hypothesis (H₀) that the data is normally distributed (where S=0 and K=3).

Fig 1 shows the distribution plots for the 3 assets

Fig 1 . Distribution plots and zoomed left tails for Nifty 50 ,USD, Gold

3.2 GARCH Volatility Filtering

Financial returns exhibit high volatility which is usually clustered, highlighted by Mandelbrot's Effect accompanied by conditional heteroskedasticity and serial autocorrelation. Moreover, EVT requires variables to be independent and identically distributed which further stresses the need for GARCH filtering.

A GARCH(1,1) model given by

$$\sigma_t^2 = \omega + \alpha \varepsilon_{\{t-1\}}^2 + \beta \sigma_{\{t-1\}}^2$$

where σ_t^2 is the conditional variance at time t, ε_{t-1} is the residual at t-1, $R_t = \mu + \varepsilon_t$ and ω, α, β are estimated parameters expresses current volatility as a multiple of , long run average variance , past volatility and past shocks. A high β in the Indian market along with parsimony principle of GARCH(1,1) justifies its use instead of higher order GARCH models.

The standardised residuals $z_t = r_t / \sigma_t$ thus form the filtered series to which EVT is subsequently applied. The adequacy of the GARCH(1,1) fit is assessed using the Ljung-Box test on both the residuals and squared residuals and the results confirm significant volatility filtering . For Nifty 50 ($p = 0.864$) and Gold ($p = 0.056$). For USD/INR ,however ,the test on residuals gives $p = 0.030$ technically rejecting the null hypothesis of no autocorrelation explained by controlled RBI structuring during stress periods but the ACF plots confirm negligibly small lags .

3.3 Threshold Selection and GPD Fitting

Standard financial models using the normal distribution essentially model the entire data set diluting the effect of extreme losses on the final model causing an underestimation of loss. Extreme Value Theory on the other hand models only the extreme values. Under the Peaks Over Threshold method, an extreme value is defined as any loss return that exceeds a carefully selected threshold u . The distribution of these exceedances $Y = X - u$ thus follows the Generalized Pareto Distribution in line with the Pickands-Balkema-de Haan Theorem with the distribution function :

$$F(x) = 1 - \left(1 + \frac{\xi x}{\beta}\right)^{-\frac{1}{\xi}}$$

where ξ is the shape parameter (tail index) and β is the scale parameter. A positive ξ implies a heavy-tailed distribution (Fréchet type) prominently seen in financial data.

This study uses Mean Excess Plots and 95% Quantile to find the threshold for each asset further validated by checking across a range of thresholds till ξ was found stable. The final GPD for each asset was fitted using Maximum Likelihood Estimation. It was found that the 95% Quantile provided a robust and stable fit across all 3 assets, the respective thresholds and parameters given in Table 2.

Table 2: Threshold Selection and GPD Parameter Estimates

Asset	Threshold (u)	Shape (ξ)	Scale (β)
Nifty 50	1.64	0.125	0.670
Gold (INR)	1.54	0.176	0.599
USD/INR	1.49	0.088	0.549

Note: All shape parameters ($\xi > 0$) confirm heavy-tailed behavior in the Fréchet domain.

3.4 Student-t Copula for Dependence Modelling

The Sklar's Theorem (1959) states that any multivariate distribution can be expressed in terms of its marginal and copula. Copula therefore is a function that joins marginal distributions to form a multivariate distribution. Portfolio risk depends not just on individual assets but also on joint behavior of assets during extreme events. Hence copula becomes extremely relevant for portfolio risk analysis. For Indian market specifically, where assets exhibit tail dependence during extreme events, the Student-t Copula proves to be a better as compared to the Gaussian Copula which assumes zero tail dependence.

The parameters of the Student-t Copula capture the shape and heaviness of the tail. The correlation matrix R provides the linear association of the variables in the model (shape of the tail) and degrees-of-freedom parameter ν determines the likeliness of joint extremes (heaviness of tail). The tail dependence parameter λ is given by

$$2t_{\nu+1} \left(-\sqrt{\frac{(\nu+1)(1-\rho)}{1+\rho}} \right)$$

where $t_{\nu+1}$ is the Student-t CDF with $\nu+1$ degrees of freedom. Lower ν implies heavier copula tails and stronger joint extreme dependence. The copula is fit to the Probability Integral Transformed (PIT) residuals $U_i = F_i(z_i)$, where F_i are the empirical CDFs of the GARCH residuals using maximum likelihood estimation and $U_i \sim Uniform(0,1)$.

Table 3: Student-t Copula Estimates and Tail Dependence Coefficients

Parameter	Estimate	Std. Error
ρ (Nifty–Gold)	–0.047	0.018
ρ (Nifty–USD/INR)	–0.233	0.016

ρ (Gold–USD/INR)	+0.256	0.016
Degrees of Freedom (ν)	7.994	0.751
Log-likelihood	320.8	—
λ Nifty–Gold	0.0119	—
λ Nifty–USD/INR	0.0042	—

Note: All correlations significant at $p < 0.01$. λ denotes lower tail dependence coefficient.

3.5 VaR and Expected Shortfall Computation

For each of the 3 portfolios for this study, that is, Equal weighted Portfolio(EWP), Hedged Equity Portfolio (HEP) and Pure Equity Portfolio(PEP) , VaR and ES values for both Gaussian and EVT-Copula models are calculated at 99% confidence level using 10,000 Monte Carlo simulations .

The Gaussian VaR is simply the 99th percentile assuming the data follows normal distribution and the ES is the average of all losses that exceed the Normal VaR.

$$VaR_N = \mu + z_p \cdot \sigma$$

$$ES_N = \mu + \sigma \cdot \frac{\phi(z_p)}{1 - p}$$

where μ is the mean return , σ is the volatility , z_p pth quartile of the standard normal distribution and $\phi(\cdot)$ is the standard normal PDF

The EVT based VaR and ES are calculated using the given formulas

$$VaR_{EVT} = u + \frac{\beta}{\xi} \left[\left(\frac{n}{n_u} (1 - \rho) \right)^{-\xi} - 1 \right]$$

$$ES_{EVT} = \frac{VaR_{EVT}}{1 - \xi} + \frac{\beta - \xi u}{1 - \xi}$$

where n is the total sample size and n_u is the number of threshold exceedances.

4. RESULTS

4.1 Normality Tests

A clear rejection of Gaussian assumptions comes from the descriptive statistic values for all 3 asset return series given in Table 4, that is, kurtosis greater than 3, non-zero skewness and extreme minimum values that are substantially larger in absolute magnitude than a normal distribution would predict. All 3 distribution graphs (Fig 1) exhibit sharp leptokurtic peaks with heavy tails that extend way beyond the normal distribution. USD/INR returns display the most extreme leptokurtosis reflecting the managed float regime under which the Reserve Bank of India periodically intervenes to smooth exchange rate movements. The Jarque-Bera test statistics too are astronomically large for all three series (58,989, 62,459, and 10,218 respectively) thus rejecting normality.

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics and Normality Test Results

Asset	Skewness	Kurtosis (Pearson)	JB Test Statistic (γ_2)
Nifty 50	0.3226	8.0081	58,989***
USD/INR	-0.7857	10.6850	62,459***
Gold	0.6142	12.9070	10,218***

Note: *** denotes rejection of normality at $p < 0.0001$. JB = Jarque–Bera test statistic. N=3829

4.2 GPD Fit and Joint Tail Dependence

Fig 2 shows the data fit for the extreme values over the Generalized Pareto Distribution. The CDF fits show near perfect fitting using the EVT method for all three assets. All three shape parameter estimates are positive, confirming that each asset's tail is of the Fréchet type conforming that large losses occur with greater frequency than the Gaussian distribution predicts. Gold exhibits the heaviest tail ($\xi = 0.176$) reflecting the episodic, sharp price corrections. Nifty 50 and USD/INR display intermediate tail heaviness ($\xi = 0.125$ and 0.088 respectively).

Fig 2: CDF plots for GPD fit of the 3 assets
 x (on log scale) against $F_u(x-u)$

The maximum likelihood based t-Copula fit shows estimated degrees of freedom of approximately 8 (Table 3) which is substantially below the Gaussian limit ($\nu \rightarrow \infty$) further confirming the underestimation of joint tail dependence during extreme events using Gaussian methods.

The correlation structure reveals several economically important relationships. Nifty 50 is mildly negatively correlated with USD/INR ($\rho = -0.233$) underlining that India being a net importer specially of oil exhibits equity market sensitivity due to changing currency rates followed by FPI outflows . Gold and USD/INR show mild positive correlation ($\rho = +0.256$) as a weaker rupee directly increases the INR price of gold. Nifty 50 and gold exhibit near-zero correlation ($\rho = -0.047$) suggesting that gold has historically been a safe haven against market volatility. The tail dependence coefficients are modest in absolute magnitude, with the highest being between Gold and USD/INR ($\lambda = 0.046$) indicating that USD and Gold assets have historically acted as hedge against equity volatility, a pattern that got disrupted in 2026 shown from the findings of this paper in further sections .

4.3. Individual Asset Risk Estimates

Table 5 presents VaR (99%) and ES (99%) for each asset under both the Gaussian and EVT-GPD frameworks. All figures are expressed in standardised return units.

Table 5: Individual Asset Risk Estimates at 99% Confidence Level

Asset	Normal VaR	EVT VaR	EVT ES	Tail Risk Gap
Nifty 50	2.364	2.833	3.769	19.84%
Gold (INR)	2.312	2.657	3.622	14.92%
USD/INR	2.322	2.441	3.135	5.13%

Note: Tail Risk Gap = (EVT VaR – Normal VaR) / Normal VaR. All estimates at 99% confidence.

The EVT-GPD VaR exceeds Normal VaR by 5.1% to 19.8% across the three assets with the largest gap observed for Nifty 50 equities. The gap is smallest for USD/INR (5.1%) reflecting the lower estimated shape parameter ($\xi = 0.088$) for the currency and RBI's managed floating rate regime.

The EVT-based Expected Shortfall is significantly higher than the VaR for each asset averaging 37-42% above the EVT-VaR suggesting that once a loss crosses the VaR threshold, the expected magnitude of that loss is substantially larger than what the VaR suggests.

4.4. Portfolio-Level Risk Estimates

Table 6 presents the full portfolio-level comparison across the three allocation scenarios. The Equal Weighted Portfolio serves as the diversified benchmark(1:1:1 division across all 3 assets), Hedged Equity Portfolio represents a typical institutional allocation combining equity with gold as a traditional safe-haven (60:40 ratio) and the Pure Equity Portfolio isolates the undiversified equity case.

Table 6: Portfolio Risk Estimates at 99% Confidence Level

Metric	EWP	HEP	PEP
Normal VaR	1.314%	1.654%	2.363%
EVT VaR	1.666%	2.076%	2.833%

Normal ES	1.504%	1.894%	2.705%
EVT ES	2.104%	2.648%	3.769%
VaR Uplift (EVT vs Normal)	+26.8%	+25.5%	+19.8%
ES Uplift (EVT vs Normal)	+11.1%	+39.8%	+39.4%

Note: VaR and ES figures expressed as percentage of portfolio value. Uplift = (EVT – Normal) / Normal.

First ,The EVT-Copula VaR consistently and substantially exceeds Normal VaR across all three portfolio allocations, with the VaR uplift ranging from 19.8% (pure Nifty) to 26.8% (equal weight).

Second, the EVT-Copula ES substantially exceeds the Normal ES for the HEP and PEP (uplift of approximately 39% in both cases) showing that the market crashes harder than predicted through VaR in either case as soon as it crosses a certain acceptable loss threshold. EWP shows a smaller ES uplift (11.1%) suggesting that the inclusion of USD/INR with a relatively lighter tail moderates the overall tail severity.

5. BACKTESTING ANALYSIS

5.1 Kupiec POF Test

With approximately 73,76 and 79 trading days observed in the 2026 backtest window for the 3 portfolios respectively from Jan 1, 2026 to April 30 ,2026, the expected number of breaches at 99% confidence is 1% of the total trading days. Table 7 provides a detailed Kupiec’s POF test summary for the VaR values of the Gaussian and EVT models. The model is tested with the null hypothesis that actual violations are in the statistically acceptable range of expected violations. It must be noted that Kupiec’s POF Test is extremely sensitive to sample size.

Table 7: Statistical Validation of 99% VaR Models (Kupiec POF Test)

Portfolio	Model	Violations	P-Value	Decision
EWP	Normal	3	0.0452	REJECT
	EVT	3	0.0452	REJECT

HEP	Normal	4	0.0084	REJECT
	EVT	3	0.0505	ACCEPT
PEP	Normal	2	0.2516	ACCEPT
	EVT	1	0.8196	ACCEPT

For HEP and PEP ,the null hypothesis being accepted for EVT VaR shows that the violations even though higher in magnitude , lie in the acceptable range of expected violations thus proving the robustness of the method as compared to the Gaussian VaR . While the individual asset tails were well modeled, the joint dependence between Gold, USD, and Equity shifted in 2026 shown by the rejection of the EWP for both models. This suggests a breakdown in diversification benefits that could not be predicted by historical data possibly due to a regime shift given the geopolitical pressures in 2026.

5.2 Descriptive Breach Analysis

Table 8 provides a detailed breakdown of the breach days and respective model accuracy in estimating the losses.

March 23 represents the most significant validation of the EVT framework in this study. Actual losses for the PEP (2.60%) and EWP (1.79%) significantly breached the Normal VaR and Normal ES thresholds whereas the EVT-ES successfully categorized these as expected tail events.

March 13 underlines an example of false risk alarm by the Normal VaR while it was considered safe by all other risk estimators that may lead to increased capital charges for a bank under Basel III .ES especially under EVT framework avoids such false signals thus avoiding panic selling in the market.

The January 30 breach is the most severe across portfolios with losses reaching as high as 4.77% likely a black swan event disrupting the diversification pattern following an extreme tail dependence across all portfolios, the estimate of which lied outside historical EVT and ES values

For PEP on 19 March, the realized loss of 3.26% falls between the Normal VaR (2.36%) and the EVT ES (3.77%), meaning the EVT ES successfully bounds the actual loss while the Normal VaR is already breached. PEP being the only portfolio that could be accurately estimated suggests that the risk was likely coming from more volatile movement in Gold or USD.

Table 8: Backtesting - Realised Losses on Breach Days vs. Model Predictions

Date	Portfolio	Actual Loss	Normal VaR	EVT VaR	Normal ES	EVT ES
2026-01-30	EWP	4.01%	BREACH	BREACH	BREACH	BREACH
	HEP	4.77%	BREACH	BREACH	BREACH	BREACH
2026-03-13	HEP	1.73%	BREACH	SAFE	SAFE	SAFE
2026-03-19	EWP	2.75%	BREACH	BREACH	BREACH	BREACH
	HEP	4.32%	BREACH	BREACH	BREACH	BREACH
	PEP	3.26%	BREACH	BREACH	BREACH	SAFE
2026-03-23	EWP	1.79%	BREACH	BREACH	BREACH	SAFE
	HEP	3.01%	BREACH	BREACH	BREACH	BREACH
	PEP	2.60%	BREACH	SAFE	SAFE	SAFE

Note: All figures are percentage losses. Breach day defined as realised loss > Normal VaR.

6. DISCUSSION

6.1 Implications for Indian Financial Risk Management

The results of this study challenges the risk assessment methods and the historical safe haven hypothesis for the Indian financial markets.

I. Systematic Underestimation and Capital Adequacy

The consistent and significant underestimation of tail risk by Gaussian VaR models ranging from 5% to 27% below the EVT-Copula models imply that capital buffers computed using standard VaR are insufficient to absorb losses during market stress episodes of the kind observed in 2008, 2013, 2020, and the early 2026 period examined here. For Indian banks and non-bank financial institutions subject to RBI capital adequacy requirements, this finding supports the adoption of internal models that incorporate EVT-based VaR estimation for risk estimation.

Fig 3:Breach Visualization Graph for HEP and PEP

a. HEP

b. PEP

II. The Diversification Paradox and Gold Financialization

2026 returns for the 3 portfolios show higher absolute values of losses for the more diversified portfolios as compared to the single asset PEP. This raises serious questions about currency and gold being considered as safety buffers during stress periods likely signifying joint crash probabilities to be much higher than historically predicted.

Moreover, despite mild negative correlation ($\rho = -0.047$) and close to zero tail dependence (0.0119) between equity and gold, HEP consistently returned the highest overall losses. This could likely be due to a sudden surge in private holding of Gold in the Indian market including religious trusts, Exchange Traded Funds (ETFs) and Gold Loan companies (NBFCs) with ETF holding increasing from approximately 59000 crore rupees in March 2025 to 1.71 Lakh Crore Rupees by March 2026 and Gold Loans accounting for 36% of the total lending as of April 2026. On the other hand, Govt holdings have risen by barely any margins. Under such a regime private players are more likely to sell a liquid asset like gold to combat liquidity crunch during stressful market conditions like the 2008 housing crisis, 2020 immediate Covid lockdown or more recently during the 2026 geopolitical tensions. This coupled with the extensive Gold rally seen in later 2025 and a possible correction, may have even led Indian households, who remain the largest holders of gold globally, to sell gold to finance liquidity.

III. Expected Shortfall (ES) as a superior risk measure

Expected Shortfall substantially exceeds VaR across both frameworks with EVT - ES more tightly realizing losses during the 2026 backtest hence supporting the idea that markets behave differently after crossing an extreme loss threshold with conditional average of losses being a more robust method than simple VaR. This is consistent with the direction of global regulatory reform under the Basel III FRTB, which mandates the use of ES rather than VaR for market risk capital requirements. The Indian regulatory framework has not yet fully adopted ES as the primary metric and the results of this study provide empirical evidence for the Indian market in support of this transition.

6.2 Limitations and Directions for Future Research

Several limitations of the study must be acknowledged. First, GARCH(1,1) with asymmetric models like EGARCH or GJR-GARCH could better capture the volatility effect and the impact of RBI intervention observed in the USD/INR residuals.

Second, while the Student-t copula proves to be better than Gaussian, moving toward Vine copulas (C-vine or D-vine) could provide a more dynamic approach to the dependence structure .

Third, the 2026 backtest ,even though meaningful ,is constrained by a short 80-day window. Further validation could provide a more accurate test for the following model .

Fourth , future models could also incorporate more weights to the present market conditions rather than solely relying on historical data , however long , keeping in mind the risk of overfitting .

7. CONCLUSION

This paper has developed and validated a GARCH-EVT-Copula framework for modelling tail risk in the Indian multi-asset market, applied to Nifty 50, Gold (INR), and USD/INR using 18 years of daily return data. Our analysis addresses a significant gap in the Indian financial risk management literature, that is, the absence of a comprehensive out of sample tested alternative to the Gaussian VaR framework that incorporates both the fat-tailed marginal asset distributions and the joint dependence structure during crashes.

Collectively, the findings provide robust evidence that Gaussian risk models understate left tailed risk in the Indian financial markets , and that the GARCH-EVT-Copula framework represents a practically feasible and substantially more accurate alternative for portfolio risk management. As Indian capital markets deepen and Indian financial institutions increase their integration with global markets, the adoption of EVT-based risk frameworks is theoretically justified and supported by 2026 evidence.

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